

ACCESS TO PRESCHOOL EDUCATION

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Abstract: Many parents know that the former child. However, this is not true, and the child needs daily confirmation that he really loves him. Love can be expressed in many ways – kind words are passed along with time and affirmation.

Keyword: preschool, education, cognitive activity, modification, communication, research, individual.

Introduction: Education is based on mutual respect and cooperation between adults and children, the necessity and openness of relationships, the commitment of children to a successful preschool education, and many opportunities for adults.

Freedom of choice allows the full child to determine the abilities that lead to this. At the same time, it is not about complete freedom without supervision by adults. Creating the necessary conditions for children to receive a comprehensive and preschool education, which allows the easiest and only knowledge and skills to be acquired in a safe environment. Point out the advantages, disadvantages, inconveniences and possible consequences of certain actions. An overview of your requirements and actions. This allows the child to understand that adults do not think about him, but teaches the necessity in danger or in life. Education and preschool children. Principles of education for children before school age Determine the work of the teacher of the preschool educational institution and the necessary knowledge necessary for the successful learning and full mastery of the child. The task of teachers and teachers in organizing the process of preschool education and training of children is to increase the general cognitive activity of children, to create the necessary conditions for the formation of a positive attitude to educational activities, independence and work. The basic principles of children’s pre-school education, the changes that have occurred in society, and the approach to children’s education are

changing. If earlier children had the correct habits of coercion and prohibitions, today modern children react to such methods.

Methods of analysis. Many parents know that the former child. However, this is not true, and the child needs daily confirmation that he really loves him. Love can be expressed in different ways - together and words of approval. Education and preschool education Children determine the work of the teacher of preschool institutions and are necessary for the successful learning and full mastery of the necessary knowledge of the child. The task of teachers and teachers in organizing the process of preschool education and training of children is to increase the general cognitive activity of children, to create the necessary conditions for the formation of a positive attitude to educational activities, independence and work.

Preschool education of children One of the main principles of education and the formation of the child's personality is systematic and sequential. In return, all skills and knowledge are given, which are associated with significant complexity. Systematic training includes the following concepts: intended educational materials should reflect different aspects of the surrounding reality and communicate into a single system of knowledge.⁵⁴

The teacher's qualifications should allow him to convey the necessary knowledge with complexity, taking into account the fact that age and ability can understand depending on age and ability; The curriculum promotes the gradual development of the stages of logical thinking and includes various components. in overcoming developing difficulties, imagination, imagination and the appearance of such signs. A visual guide can serve any material or character model. However, you need to understand that this is just a means of knowledge and not a goal. Therefore, when using them, it is necessary to take into account its content and feedback. Children's education and preschool education should be based on an individual approach, taking into account the individual characteristics of the child's character, his character, inclinations and abilities.

An individual approach to education and training significantly increases the effectiveness of classes and allows you to reveal talents even more at an early age.⁵⁵ Preschool education thanks to an individual approach. Children, the teacher can fully

⁵⁴ Burkhanova M.G. (2021). SOCIO-PHILOSOPHICAL LOOK OF A CULTURAL MAN. ISJ Theoretical & Applied Science, 12 (104), 422-425.

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⁵⁵ Burkhanova M.G. (2022). AXIOLOGICAL ANALYSIS OF STUDENT MORALITY. European journal of research development and sustainability. Vol 3 N 2. <https://www.scholarzest.com/>

study the child's personality and determine the factors that have a serious impact on him.

Competent preschool education of children, constant monitoring of children, understanding of the characteristics of relationships between children.

Children's preschool education: From 4 to 6 years old, psychologists call it a relatively quiet period. Education of junior preschool children 4-5 years is relatively easy: the baby is calm, obedient, sleeps and eats, is not very careful.

The upbringing and development of a child 6 years and older means great patience and the ability to negotiate. If the child has love and care in the family, it will be a little different in the kindergarten. Folk peers are not always as friendly as parents. Therefore, friction, quarrels, conflicts may arise. Nevertheless, communication with children is more preferable and interesting for the child.

Results and analysis. Try to make the child have a bright and good perception of life. You often love him, hug him, kiss him, praise him. This is very important for preschool education. Your care, attention and love give the child a sense of security, and later this feeling turns into confidence in his own abilities.

Conclusion. Children's preschool education is, first of all, the desire to understand them and to do like them. If your baby is afraid of someone - for example, the house or garbage, - play with him mythical characters Show them well and comfortably. Such preschool education helps the baby to cope with fear. Do not watch psychologists specializing in the education of young preschoolers, arrange noisy games while lying down, do not read scary fairy tales, doctors about chancellors and evil magicians.

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